

Rice-based cropping sequence for rainfed low-lands of eastern Uttar Pradesh

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Farmers in eastern UP usually plant linseed, lentil, and wheat Dec-Apr after wet season rice. Yields are low because of lack of fertilizer and poor field

preparation that results in cloddy surface soil, loss of moisture, and delayed planting. This gives poor plant stands and yields.

We studied the effect of three tillage methods and three fertility levels on three crops in dry seasons 1987-88 and 1988-89 (see table). Experimental soil was sandy to clay loam with pH 8.1, 0.35% organic C, 11 kg available P and 250 kg K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Rice variety Madhukar was transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing the second week of Jul with 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Wheat HUW234, lentil PL406, and linseed Mukta were sown the first week of Dec.

Wheat sown after rice in a well-prepared field with NP fertilizer gave the highest gross return (\$634/ha), followed by lentil (\$615/ha). Lentil sown in a well-prepared field with NP fertilizer had highest net return (\$307/ha), followed by wheat (\$288/ha). ■

Grain yield and gross and net return from dry season crops in a rice-based cropping system.^a Uttar Pradesh, India, Dec-Apr 1987-89.

Crop sequence ^b	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)				Gross return (\$/ha)			Net return (\$/ha)			Benefit:cost ratio		
	Rice	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3
Rice - wheat + no NP	2.4	1.69	1.12	1.22	460	424	437	153	139	139	1.49	1.48	1.46
Rice - wheat + 60 kg N/ha	2.4	2.45	1.58	1.85	593	483	517	265	177	198	1.80	1.57	1.62
Rice - What + 60 kg N + 13 P/ha	2.4	2.76	2.02	2.08	634	539	546	288	215	209	1.83	1.66	1.62
Rice - linseed +no NP	2.4	0.40	0.38	0.33	431	428	393	145	164	116	1.50	1.62	1.41
Rice - linseed + 40 N	2.4	0.60	0.66	0.48	513	534	465	216	259	176	1.72	1.94	1.60
Rice - linseed + 40 N + 8.8 P	2.4	0.72	0.75	0.57	557	567	501	251	283	204	1.82	1.99	1.68
Rice - lentil +no NP	2.4	0.53	0.40	0.48	474	426	455	191	164	180	1.67	1.62	1.65
Rice - lentil + 20 N	2.4	0.83	0.69	0.75	582	531	555	291	261	272	2.00	1.96	1.96
Rice - lentil + 20 N + 13 P	2.4	0.92	0.83	0.89	615	582	604	307	296	305	1.99	2.03	2.02

^aT1 = well-prepared field, T2 = zero tillage (Paraquat sprayed on paddy stubble 2 d before sowing), T3 = stubble cut with shavers and seed sown behind the tine. USS1 = Rs 16.32. ^bN and P in kg/ha. ^cAv of 2 yr.

Rice-based cropping sequence for irrigated fields

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Wet season rice followed by dry season wheat occupies most of the area under irrigation. We evaluated other crop sequences in 1986-87 and 1987-88 at CRS.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 8.0, 0.32% organic C, 29 kg available P, and 243 kg K/ha.

Rice variety NDR80 was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing during wet season (Jul-Oct) followed by wheat cultivar HUW234, barley Azad, pea Rachna, lentil PL 406, chickpea G130, linseed Mukta, and mustard Varuna in dry season (Nov-Apr) or green gram T44, black gram T9, and maize Kanchan in summer (Apr-Jun). The experiment was laid out

in a randomized block design with three replications.

Rice received 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha. All crops were grown with recommended inputs and practices.

Highest total grain yield (7 t/ha) was with rice - maize, followed by rice -

wheat (6.7 t/ha) (see table). Rice - wheat had the highest gross income followed by rice - chickpea. Rice - lentil had the highest net profit (\$333/ha) and benefit:cost ratio (2.08), followed by rice - wheat (\$319/ha). ■

Grain yield and net income of different rice-based cropping sequences.^a Uttar Pradesh, India 1986-88.

Crop sequence	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)			Total cost (\$/ha)	Gross income (\$/ha)	Net income (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio
	Wet season	Dry season	Summer				
Rice - fallow	3.0	-	-	209	298	89	1.42
Rice - wheat - fallow	3.0	3.7	-	412	731	319	1.77
Rice - barley - fallow	3.0	3.2	-	363	597	234	1.64
Rice - pea - fallow	3.0	1.4	-	350	653	303	1.86
Rice - chickpea - fallow	3.0	1.2	-	357	663	306	1.85
Rice - lentil - fallow	3.0	1.4	-	308	641	333	2.08
Rice - linseed - fallow	3.0	1.0	-	307	541	234	1.76
Rice - mustard - fallow	3.0	1.0	-	330	389	259	1.78
Rice - fallow - green gram	3.0	-	0.7	322	467	145	1.45
Rice - fallow - black gram	3.0	-	0.8	321	477	156	1.48
Rice - fallow - maize	3.0	-	4.0	363	543	180	1.49

^aUSS1 = Rs 16.32. ^bAv of 2 yr.